

THE RISE OF THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM IN HUMAN INTERESTS AND ITS REFLECTION IN THE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY

Abduganiyev Temurbek Alimardon oqli

Namangan state university, Faculty of Law,
student of 2-group. Tel: 93 401 15 11 .

temurbekabduganiyev402@gmail.com.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7470026>

Abstract. This article reflects information and opinions about the protection of human interests and the development of the judicial system, the benefits of the decisions being made for our people.

Key words: Strategy, justice, modernization, legality, application, reform, power, principle, corruption, codification.

ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЕ СУДЕБНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ В ИНТЕРЕСАХ ЧЕЛОВЕКА И ЕЕ ОТРАЖЕНИЕ В СТРАТЕГИИ РАЗВИТИЯ

Аннотация. В данной статье отражены сведения и мнения о защите интересов человека и развитии судебной системы, пользе принимаемых решений для нашего народа.

Ключевые слова: Стратегия, справедливость, модернизация, законность, применение, реформа, власть, принцип, коррупция, кодификация.

INSON MANFAATLARIDA SUD-HUQUQ TIZIMING YUKSALISHI VA "TARAQQIYOT STRATEGIYASI" DA AKS ETISHI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada inson manfaatlarini himoya qilish va sud-huquq tizimining rivoji, qabul qilinayotgan qarorlarning xalqimiz uchun manfaati to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar va fikr mulohazalar o'z aksini topgan.

Kalit so'zlar: strategiya, adolat, modernizatsiya, odil sudlov, qonuniylik, ariza, islohot, hokimiyat, tamoyil, korrupsiya, kodifikatsiyalash.

Our great grandfather Abu bakir Khorazmiy, who lived and created in the 10th century, said this about the government: "If justice does not reign around the government, it will face a crisis" Indeed, these wisdoms are being proven in practice today. The reforms being carried out to achieve an independent, open and transparent judicial system in our country are being further improved. It is necessary for judges to become real defenders of justice and law, which is being strengthened within the framework of the law. If we pay attention to the socioeconomic, spiritual and educational reforms being carried out in the life of our country today, as well as the issued laws, decisions, decrees and orders, we can easily say that a new era has been created in the reforms of judicial system. First of all, reliable protection of citizens' rights

and freedoms, ensuring judicial independence, achieving justice, strengthening legality, effective fight against corruption are important in achieving fundamental modernization of the state. During the past period, largescale work was carried out in Uzbekistan, along with all other fields, in the field of judicial law. The importance of the Constitution in the development of our country, the development of our society, and the provision of human rights and freedoms is incomparable. It has a special place in ensuring the human rights and freedoms enshrined in the Constitution, ensuring legality in society and the true independence of the judiciary.

In particular, Article 12 of our Constitution states that "Judges are independent and subject only to the law. It is not allowed to interfere with the activities of judges in the administration of justice in any way, and such interference is a cause of responsibility according to the law. Immunity of judges is guaranteed by law. Judges cannot be senators, deputies of representative bodies of state power. Judges can be members of political parties, participate in

political activities, as well as engage in any other types of paid activities, except scientific and pedagogical activities. No. A judge may be released from his duties as a judge before the end of his term of office only if there are grounds specified by law." [1]. This norm is the legal basis for the freedom of activity of judges, their rights and obligations are protected by law. It is worth noting that one of the main reasons for guaranteeing the independence of judges and only obeying the law at the level of the constitution is explained by the fact that the judiciary is given a right that does not apply to the authority of any other body the right to administer justice. After all, the importance of justice in the life of our country, in achieving the full protection of the rights and freedoms of our citizens, is incomparable. At this point, it is appropriate to emphasize that justice has been glorified and appreciated in all eras, and people have strived for it. In particular, the Roman philosophers "Pereat mundus et fiat justitia", that is, "let the world perish, but let justice prevail"[2]. it is not for nothing that they have emphasized. Although these classic slogans of Roman philosophers are exaggeration at first glance, they value justice so highly.

In the early years of independence, a number of our laws were adopted aimed at implementing the principle of independence of judges and obedience only to the law, provided for in the Constitution. The Criminal Code adopted in 1994, the Code of Criminal Procedure, the Code of Administrative Responsibilities and the Codes of Civil Procedure and Economic Procedure adopted in 1997, the Law "On Courts", 0¹ A number of decrees and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Government decisions can be cited.

However, an in-depth analysis of the development path of our country, today's world market situation has changed dramatically, and the competition is becoming more and more intense in the conditions of globalization. was demanding implementation. Ensuring the true independence of the judiciary has become a vital necessity for the beginning of a completely new stage aimed at increasing the public's confidence in justice. Any reforms and opportunities, social processes taking place in the life of the society and the state have a certain basis and support. The decision "On measures to fundamentally improve the system of retraining of employees, their qualification improvement" and the establishment of the Higher School of Judges based on it, and the fact that only students who graduated from this school can participate in the competitions announced for the position of judge, was an important step in the reforms of the judicial system. It is known that on September 20, 2021, "On amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Supreme Council of Judges of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [3]. The Law of the

Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted. Until then, the Council had one of the powers, such as forming a reserve of candidates for judicial positions. This, by itself, required additional efforts and expenses to form a pool of candidates for the position of judge, and led to the restriction of the rights of the candidates participating in the Higher School entrance exams. Also, by today, the institution of reservation for judges has lost its meaning, therefore, due to the fact that the era itself requires the termination of the institution of reservations for judges, and in connection with the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Courts" on July 28, 2021, Article 7 of the Law appropriate changes and additions have been made.

For the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, a system was established to appeal to the court against the decisions and illegal actions of state bodies and officials. This system, which was created in order to ensure the constitutional right in practice, began to bear its results in a short period of time. Such reforms contribute to the establishment and development of a legal-democratic state. For example, in the article "Strategic reforms in the judicial system serve the interests of people" by Nilufar

Nodirkhonova, head of the department of the "Strategy of Development" center, we can see the following information: "During 2019 and 2020, administrative courts 31,321 applications were considered, of which 21,272 or about 67.9% were satisfied. In particular, 2,852 decisions of governors were declared illegal, and the violated rights of citizens and legal

entities were restored. In the past 4 years, 2,770 people were acquitted, and in 2020, 781 people were acquitted, 3,434 people were released from the courtroom, and 5,958 people were unjustly punished. the articles were dropped or changed from the charges. This is, without a doubt, one of the great achievements in the field of judicial law." [4]

According to the experience of developed and highly developed countries, each nation takes a rightful place in the world community by setting great and promising goals and having the potential to realize them. It is no exaggeration to say that today Uzbekistan is at such a responsible crossroads in its history. Therefore, on January 28 of this year, the

President signed the decree "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" for 2022-2026. According to the information of the "Development Strategy" center, the draft of this document was discussed by the public through the portals 2022-2026.strategy.uz, regulation.gov.uz, and public.uz from December 30 of last year to January 15, 2022. held. The strategy consists of 7 directions and 100 goals. The State program for the implementation of the development strategy in 2022 envisages the allocation of funds in the amount of 55 trillion soums and 11.7 billion US dollars for the financing of the planned activities. This strategy is turning into a national idea that represents an important and new era stage that will decide the fate of our future.

So what is the strategy? How does it serve the people's goals? What are the prospects of the chosen goals?

Strategy is a system of finding, articulating, and developing doctrine that, when consistently and thoroughly implemented, will ensure long-term

success. By the 21st century, the concept of strategy has expanded considerably. The term strategy covers the concepts of management organization aimed at forecasting and eliminating crisis situations that have arisen in the economic, socio-political and other spheres of the world and in the internal life of the state. Based on this, the state strategy is expressed in many concepts that are interconnected with each other, but acquire a separate character.

The 14th goal of the presidential decree "On Development Strategy" is called "Ensuring the rule of law and constitutional legitimacy and establishing human dignity as the main criterion of this process" and includes the following necessary tasks: to ensure labor, social security and other internationally recognized rights of persons with disabilities, to introduce effective mechanisms to assist their social adaptation and reintegration into society, to establish joint activities of state and community institutions in this direction. Legal impact on citizens, including the unconditional provision of legality in the application of measures related to restrictions on freedom of movement, and strengthening of public control through the introduction of digital technologies. Simplification and creation of additional conveniences for the population started in this direction to complete the reforms. Consistent continuation of the policy of improvement of criminal, criminal-procedural and criminal executive legislation, wide implementation of the principle of humanitarianism in the system of criminal punishments and their execution. Improvement of preventive mechanisms for the prevention of torture and adoption of a special law in this direction. Formation of juvenile justice system and codification of child rights legislation." [5]. By turning the principle of "law is priority, punishment is inevitable" into the main criterion, creating strong legal foundations of open and fair prosecution activities, strengthening control over search and investigation activities, and introducing effective mechanisms to effectively protect the dignity and freedom of citizens Tasks have been defined, such as the fundamental reform of the system of recording information about crimes in law enforcement agencies, the use of modern methods to prevent cases of concealment of crimes. Another main goal is to ensure the timely and complete execution of documents of courts and other bodies introduction of effective enforcement mechanisms, expansion of the scope of use of alternative, non-judicial methods of execution of documents of courts and other bodies.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the Constitution of our country and the laws adopted on this basis play an important role in increasing the authority of judicial bodies in the society, ensuring the true independence of judges and their work only based on the laws. Every citizen living in the Republic of Uzbekistan knows that the law not only exists, but that it is implemented in a fair way, so that every citizen can live comfortably and get benefits through the laws. It is one of the conditions. It can be seen that ensuring the rule of law, which is an urgent link of reforms in New Uzbekistan, is taking strategic steps to reform the legal system and protect the rights and interests of citizens. Undoubtedly, these fundamental changes are an expression of practical work carried out in the interests of the people.

REFERENCES

1. CONSTITUTION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. 08.12.1992.
2. V, Topildiyev, Roman law, Tashkent (generation of the new century) 64 pages.
3. <https://lex.uz/docs/-5643174> .
4. <https://strategy.uz/index.php?news=1442>. "Strategic reforms in the judicial system serve human interests." N. Nodirkhonova, Head of the Department of Development Strategy Center. 25.11.2021.
5. <http://lex.uz//uz/docs/-5841063>. PF-60 on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, Tashkent city, 01.28.2022.